

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL POSSIBILITIES OF SOCIALIZATION OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14160041>

Abstract. *In this article, the significance of socialization of elementary school students today, pedagogical-psychological possibilities, various methods of socialization of students are discussed and conclusions are drawn.*

Keywords: *society, socialization, pedagogy, psychology, primary class, opportunity, thinking.*

In today's society, the amount of information and the number of news are increasing day by day in every field. This puts a number of tasks in front of the person. One of them is to find a suitable place for the person in the society, to always maintain the position of an active citizen, and to socialize. Taking into account this task in society, we are required to systematically implement the processes of socialization of future citizens, that is, elementary school students.

Socialization means the process of mastering certain knowledge, norms and value system by a person, which allows a person to function as a full-fledged member of society. The successful completion of this process depends on the active position of the person and the extent to which the person has mastered the social experience. The process of socialization has a stepwise character, which ultimately determines the degree of socialization of a person. It is very important for students to find their place in society. The reason is that the individual cannot develop without society. In order for a person to develop directly, to be able to demonstrate his personal abilities, he must be socialized.

Socialization in pedagogy is the process of every person joining society, accepting its norms, requirements, expectations and influence, showing it in every action and behavior and, if necessary, being able to influence others with this social experience. Socialization as a central problem of the teaching of social learning emerged in America at the end of the 30s of the 20th century as a strong psychological direction of social learning. Several generations of researchers have been working in the field of socialization for a long time. These generations are distinguished in American psychology itself. The first generation (30-60s of the 20th century) - N. Miller, D. Dollard, R. Sears, B. Whiting, B. Skinner, these researchers are still included in the theory of social learning by behaviorism. The second generation (60-70 years) — A. Bandura, R. Waters, S. Biju, D. Gevirt and others. The third generation (since 70) - V. Hartup, E. Maccoby, D. Aronfried, W. Branfenbrenner and others. Most of the Eastern thinkers expressed their views on the socialization of the individual. The thinker and statesman Yusuf Khos Khajib in his work "Qutadgu Bilik" revealed the essence of the issue of socialization with the help of 4 images. The first is justice in the form of King Kuntugdi, the second is the state, the minister Oytoldi, the third is intelligence, the minister's son Ogdilmish, the fourth is satisfaction depicted as his relative Ozgirmish. Russian sociologist A. Antonov said that the family, as a socio-psychological unit, has such normative and

informational effects on the individual that, as a result, the child acquires the legal norms and behavior patterns of the society.[1]

In the process of socialization of children, the following features are distinguished: Unlike adults, who change their behavior more often than their attitudes (i.e., they are capable of self-regulation, individually and socially relevant actions), children adapt basic value orientations reinforced at the level of emotional-value relations in community entry process;

adults can assess social norms and have a critical attitude towards them; children include them as established regulators of behavior;

socialization of children is based on obedience to adults, compliance with certain rules and requirements (without assessment and reflection processes); adult socialization is aimed at mastering certain skills (operational-technical sphere), in children the leading role is occupied by behavioral motivation (motivation-need sphere).

In the process of socialization, the child acquires various knowledge about society, social relations, social status, norms and rules of social behavior, various skills and abilities that help him get used to society. This process takes place very rapidly, especially in childhood. It is known that a child receives a lot of knowledge before the age of five, which will be reflected in his later life.

A distinguishing feature of the child's socialization is that it is difficult for him to evaluate and control the norms of behavior promoted by society. He only learns these things, that's why parents, relatives, professionals working with them (psychologist, doctor, pedagogue, etc.) have a great influence in the process of socialization of the child's personality. It is up to them to strive to enslave them in life. It is related to social pedagogy, that in the process of learning in a school or other educational institution, a child first of all acquires academic knowledge. However, at the same time, certain systematic social knowledge, skills and competencies are formed in it. These knowledge, skills and abilities are very necessary in the process of socialization - when the child needs special help. It is called imparting social knowledge to help the child's socialization, formation of social skills and competences. Socialization of a child is a complex and continuous process. On the one hand, any society develops certain social and moral values, behavior, moral laws and norms at the stage of its development. The society envisages living and working as an equal member of this society, adopting the laws and regulations of this society. For this, the society influences the individual through the norms of education. On the other hand, various events taking place in the surrounding world do not fail to show its influence on formation. Society includes various interacting social institutions. Through these, the process of acquisition of social norms by the child is realized.

The process of socialization is formed and develops in the process of adaptation of students to the class team, school team and interaction with them during primary education. Various team games conducted during the lessons are very effective in this process. There are various factors that affect the socialization process of a child. A factor is a significant condition, driving force, and cause. Among the factors of socialization, the system of educating the young generation has a special place. Society exerts mass, collective, group and individual influence on every child through institutions. The socialization of a child's personality occurs under the influence of various factors, which is confirmed by many studies in social pedagogy and sociology. Factors of human socialization include:

1) microfactors - immediate environment of the child's life, immediate social environment: family, neighbors, children's community, microsociety;

2) mesofactors - ethnic-social-cultural conditions of the region, subculture, mass media, type of settlement (metropolis, medium-sized city, small city; port, industry, resort center, industrial-cultural; rural - large, medium, small);

3) macro factors - country, ethnic origin, society, state (as a certain socio-economic, socio-political system in which the entire process of human life takes place);

4) megafactors - space, planet, world, related to national, regional, continental and global aspects of human development.

In short, it is possible to achieve the goal by introducing different approaches, methods and technologies to the lesson processes, relying on all the factors listed above in the process of socialization of elementary school students. Socialization is considered as an endless process and is not limited to any age period, on the contrary, it is a continuous process related to the acquisition of social skills throughout the life of an individual. The success of this process depends on many factors. It is possible to control the process of socialization of students by applying these factors at the right time in the primary education process.

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